

Description of Kumari Puja and her glory as reflected in Devi Bhagavata.

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Abstract :

Devi Bhagavatam is a sacred scripture of Sanatan Dharma. Here in the Shakta sect of Hinduism, Mahashakti is considered the original creator of the universe. Goddess Sattwara is said to be the source and savior of all living beings. The origin of the female race from the elements of nature. In this book, the divine feminine is depicted as the creator, protector and pervader of the world. During Durga Puja, Kumari is worshiped as goddess. Here, Kumari is worshiped as Durga, Kalyani, Kalika, Chandika, Shambavi, Rohini and Subhadra etc. The goddess who destroys enemies, sorrows, poor etc. and shows the way to liberation is worshiped and praised as Kumari Devi. It is forbidden to worship extra-ages as virgins beyond the age of one year and ten years. In Puranas, daughters of all races can be worshiped as virgins. All the Gods and Goddesses are pleased when women are worshipped.

keywords : Devi Bhagavatam, the virgin, A piece of nature, The women, divinity, the worship, prayer, Salvation etc.

Introduction:

Devi Bhagavatam is a sacred Purana written in Sanskrit language. This Purana consists of twelve skandhas following Srimad Bhagavatam. Although there is a difference of opinion as to whether it is Mahapurana or Upapurana, it is regarded as Mahapurana in India. In this text, devisattva is referred to as the source of all beings, the creator, the creator, the destroyer and the protector. All the subjects of this Purana revolve around the primordial divinity. Here special emphasis is laid on the devotional worship of Mahashakti. In the worship of this great power, Kumari Puja occupies a prominent place in India. Especially in Baṅgadēśē, a wide prevalence and promotion of Kumari Puja can be observed.

Rationale of the study :

The origin of women's nature is from the germs. Therefore, the power of the goddess lies in the virgin, the nature of the virgin or the female race is the nature and state of the seed. Therefore, the goddess is imposed on the virgin woman and she is pursued. The reason for this research is to present all this information to the society.

Objective of the study :

The chosen topic of my research work is very helpful and necessary to know the history of society and culture. So I started this research for this purpose and I hope this research will reveal many unknown aspects and new information about 'Kumari Pooja and her Mahatma'. Moreover, the main aim of Kumari Puja is to respect women by restraining the inner beast of the man's mind.

Hypothesis :

I have tried to uncover many unknown stories about the divinity in the female body, her influence and glory in the society by sheltering the chosen topic

'Virgin worship and her greatness as reflected in Devi Bhagavata' - that's the aim of my plan.

Methodology :

The topic of my research work belongs to qualitative research. This research work is based on society and literature. So this research has followed the descriptive method and this design or method shelters Description of Kumari Puja and her glory as reflected in Devi Bhagavata has been analyzed.

Data Collection:-

The following items have been prescribed as instruments of data collection.

Primary Data : Among the various libraries are the Sanskrit Sahitya Parishad and the National Library.

Secondary Data: Mainly Panchanan Tarkaratna's Devabhagavatam book and various text books are prescribed as reference material.

Discussion :

Kumari Puja is the worship of living energy. Every woman is the embodiment of Jaganmata. All women in this world are the embodiment of the Goddess. But the pure virgin is the most manifestation of this great power of the Goddess. For this reason, daily Kumari Puja is practiced in Mahatheerth Kamakshya and Kanyakumari and in the major Shakta Peethasthans of India. The greatest manifestation of God is in human beings. And among human beings, those who are honest and pure, the power of God is relatively greater. On the other hand, due to the pure nature of small children, the influence of divine nature is more in them. That is why the holy virgin is worshipped.

Why are women worshiped as virgins?

This worship is the worship of women's sacred life consciousness, the worship of woman's femininity, the worship of intense love for women. It is said in Devi Bhagavat that women are Shaktirupa. Lakshmi Swarupa of the world. Respecting and honoring them makes the family

beautiful and all aspects of life become good. And women should always remember their divine nature. That's why women should first of all instill immense respect within themselves and become aware of the great power that resides in their hearts. They must not limit your heart to feminine consciousness only, but establish unity with the Eternal Power Consciousness. In this way, if they are eternally strong, they will achieve the good of the society, the country and the ten. Moreover, the purity of motherhood and eternal love can be observed more in unmarried women. In a pure heart, eternal love, purity and mercy prevail in a virgin. And for this reason, Kumari Puja is practiced.

In Kumari Puja, the girl's age and deity are revealed.

It is recorded in the Puranas that two-year-old girls are called 'Kumari'. Three-year-old girls are called Trimurti, four-year-old girls are Kalyani, five-year-old girls are Rohini, six-year-old girls are Kalika, seven-year-old girls are Chandika, eight-year-old girls are Shambavi, nine-year-old girls are Durga and ten-year-old girls are called Subhadra. It is said. His over-age daughter should not be worshipped, as she is not eligible for worship in any way.

Women excluded from Kumari Puja.

Virginizing a one-year-old girl in Kumari Puja is prohibited once. Because that girl is inexperienced in smelling things. A woman above ten years of age should never be worshipped. Because she is not worthy of receiving any work worship. Moreover, girls who are discolored, blind from birth, very thin, ugly, one-eyed, full of body hair, full of pimples, body odor, menstruating, missing one finger or toe, pubic marks, widowhood and unmarried pregnancy etc. can never be worshipped as virgins.

Kumari Puja is well known.

Brahmin girls, Kshatriya girls, Vaishya girls and Shudra girls can be worshipped as virgins only if they are good-looking. A Brahmin girl can be a virgin for all kinds of work, a Kshatriya girl for joy, a Vaishya girl for profit and a Shudra girl for happiness. However, the auspicious girl of any caste is worshipped as a virgin. Because the divine power is present in the auspicious girl. Therefore, even today in Belur Math, the auspicious girl of any race is worshipped as a virgin.

Philosophical theory of virgin worship.

Paramartha philosophy and attainment of paramartha in women. In the universe, the trinity of creation, stability and harmony is constantly being achieved. Kumari Prakriti or the symbol and germ of the female race. Therefore, a virgin or a woman is worshipped by deification.

Timings of Kumari Puja

The Devi Bhagavata mentions worshipping the virgin with ornaments and rich food items daily for nine days from Ashwin's Shukla Pratipada to Mahanavami. In fact, Kumari is worshiped during this period to worship the Sattvic aspect of Mahashakti.

Prayer to Goddess Kumari

Following are the prayers mentioned by Devi Kumari:-

1. I worship the goddess Kumari, who created the gods in play and revealed all the mysteries to the boys.
2. She who exists in various forms in order of the various forms of the three qualities of the sattva, I bow down to the Trikalvyapini Trimurti of the Supreme Power.
3. I bow down to Siddhidayini Kalyani, the all-pervading one who does the welfare of the devotees if she is worshiped daily.
4. I pray to Rohini Devi, the goddess who sprouts all the pre-born karmic seeds of a lifetime.
5. We worship Goddess Kalika, who is always present in the universe in the form of Kalpantakala Mahakali.
6. I bow down to Goddess Chandika who killed Chanda-Munda and removed the sins of the devotees.
7. We worship the all-blissful Goddess Shambavi, whose form is the Vedas, whose cause of origin is not fixed in the Vedas.
8. Durgati - Salutations to Goddess Durga, destroyer and savior.
9. Salutations to Goddess Subhadra, the bestower of welfare, for warding off the evils of the devotees.

The greatness of Kumari Puja

Various greatneses of Devi Kumari are mentioned. They are-

1. By worshipping Dwivarshiya Kumari, one gets rid of misery and poverty, destruction of enemies and wealth, increase in life and strength.
2. Trimurti Kumari bestows sons and grandsons, age and trivargaphal etc.
3. (3)Kalyani Kumari bestows knowledge, victory, kingdom and happiness.
4. Rohini Kumaridevi kills diseases.
5. Kalika Kumari destroys enemies. Kumari Chandika gives wealth and wealth.
6. Shambavi Kumari hypnotizes enemies.
7. Durganamika Kumari bestows victory, annihilation of enemies, annihilation of durgati and patriot happiness etc. in struggle.
8. Banchitasiddhi Kumari Subhadra always gives.
9. Worshipping newly born daughters with devotion gives all the above results.

Recommendations :

Striratna is the chief of all gems. In a family where women are respected, the gods are pleased. And where women are not respected, all the yajna activities fail. A family in which women are always sad dies quickly. A family in which women are not sad always prospers. The effects of nature are described as the power of various goddesses. In this world, all women are the offspring of nature. Therefore, if women are respected, nature is also happy. In my opinion, if not only the virgins, but the entire female race is respected in the knowledge of the goddess, all the great works of the country will be completed auspiciously.

conclusions :

Awakening the inherent divine power in the female body through Kumari Puja. Thinking of the welfare of all people, including the afflicted, through the lotus feet of His worshipers. In the Puranas, women are always protected with care. Neglecting the wife may cause grief to the patriarch and even later to the patriarch. Society is still suffering. However, if not only virgins but all women are worshiped with devotion and faith, the whole country will improve along with social change.

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